

Electronic Supplementary Material (ESM):

Figure S4-1. *Monthly Quantile-Kendall Plots by Site*

These plots are summarized in ESM Appendix S4 (see "ESM Appendixes, Figures, and Tables"). This file contains 120 Quantile-Kendall plots (Hirsch, 2018) showing 1994-2016 trends in stream discharge, by month, for the ten streamgage trend sites used in this study (Fig. 1 and Table 1 in paper). The analysis includes daily mean-discharge records for the period April 1, 1994, through March 31, 2016 (climatic years). The explanation for color coding of points appears in the first plot, showing the likelihood that the trend direction is correct. The daily non-exceedance probability (horizontal axis) corresponds to daily discharge ranks (from lowest to highest) during each month, with low flows on the left and high flows on the right. The trend slope in percent change per year (vertical axis) shows trend in daily discharge for a given non-exceedance probability over the 1994-2016 period. The site names correspond to U.S. Geological Survey streamgage names; Table 1 (in paper) provides additional site details.

The trend slopes are computed using the Thiel-Sen slope estimator of the logarithms of the values shown and then transformed to percentage changes per year. The strength of the statistical evidence for these trends are evaluated using the Mann-Kendall trend test, adjusted for serial correlation. The strength of the evidence is characterized by the likelihood that the direction of the estimated trend is correct, computed from the Mann-Kendall test p-values as $[1 - (p/2)]$. Additional information on Quantile-Kendall plots including the calculation of likelihood values appears in the paper and in ESM Appendix S1. Further description of the method and the associated software can be obtained from <https://owi.usgs.gov/blog/Quantile-Kendall/>.

Reference:

Hirsch, R.M., 2018. Daily streamflow trend analysis: U.S. Geological Survey Office of Water Information Blog, 38 p., at: <https://owi.usgs.gov/blog/Quantile-Kendall/>.

RIVER RAISIN NEAR MONROE, MI January

RIVER RAISIN NEAR MONROE, MI February

RIVER RAISIN NEAR MONROE, MI

March

RIVER RAISIN NEAR MONROE, MI

April

RIVER RAISIN NEAR MONROE, MI

May

RIVER RAISIN NEAR MONROE, MI

June

RIVER RAISIN NEAR MONROE, MI

July

Daily non-exceedance probability

RIVER RAISIN NEAR MONROE, MI

August

Daily non-exceedance probability

RIVER RAISIN NEAR MONROE, MI September

RIVER RAISIN NEAR MONROE, MI October

RIVER RAISIN NEAR MONROE, MI November

RIVER RAISIN NEAR MONROE, MI December

Maumee River at Waterville OH January

Maumee River at Waterville OH February

Maumee River at Waterville OH March

Maumee River at Waterville OH April

Maumee River at Waterville OH

May

Maumee River at Waterville OH

June

Maumee River at Waterville OH

July

Maumee River at Waterville OH

August

Maumee River at Waterville OH September

Maumee River at Waterville OH October

Maumee River at Waterville OH November

Maumee River at Waterville OH December

MAUMEE RIVER AT NEW HAVEN, IN January

MAUMEE RIVER AT NEW HAVEN, IN February

MAUMEE RIVER AT NEW HAVEN, IN March

MAUMEE RIVER AT NEW HAVEN, IN April

MAUMEE RIVER AT NEW HAVEN, IN May

MAUMEE RIVER AT NEW HAVEN, IN June

MAUMEE RIVER AT NEW HAVEN, IN July

MAUMEE RIVER AT NEW HAVEN, IN August

MAUMEE RIVER AT NEW HAVEN, IN September

MAUMEE RIVER AT NEW HAVEN, IN October

MAUMEE RIVER AT NEW HAVEN, IN November

MAUMEE RIVER AT NEW HAVEN, IN December

ST. JOSEPH RIVER NEAR FORT WAYNE, IN January

ST. JOSEPH RIVER NEAR FORT WAYNE, IN February

ST. JOSEPH RIVER NEAR FORT WAYNE, IN March

ST. JOSEPH RIVER NEAR FORT WAYNE, IN April

ST. JOSEPH RIVER NEAR FORT WAYNE, IN May

ST. JOSEPH RIVER NEAR FORT WAYNE, IN June

ST. JOSEPH RIVER NEAR FORT WAYNE, IN July

Daily non-exceedance probability

ST. JOSEPH RIVER NEAR FORT WAYNE, IN August

Daily non-exceedance probability

ST. JOSEPH RIVER NEAR FORT WAYNE, IN September

ST. JOSEPH RIVER NEAR FORT WAYNE, IN October

ST. JOSEPH RIVER NEAR FORT WAYNE, IN November

ST. JOSEPH RIVER NEAR FORT WAYNE, IN December

ST. MARYS RIVER AT DECATUR, IN January

ST. MARYS RIVER AT DECATUR, IN February

ST. MARYS RIVER AT DECATUR, IN March

Daily non-exceedance probability

ST. MARYS RIVER AT DECATUR, IN April

Daily non-exceedance probability

ST. MARYS RIVER AT DECATUR, IN

May

Daily non-exceedance probability

ST. MARYS RIVER AT DECATUR, IN

June

Daily non-exceedance probability

ST. MARYS RIVER AT DECATUR, IN July

ST. MARYS RIVER AT DECATUR, IN August

ST. MARYS RIVER AT DECATUR, IN September

ST. MARYS RIVER AT DECATUR, IN October

ST. MARYS RIVER AT DECATUR, IN November

ST. MARYS RIVER AT DECATUR, IN December

ST. MARYS RIVER NEAR FORT WAYNE, IN January

ST. MARYS RIVER NEAR FORT WAYNE, IN February

ST. MARYS RIVER NEAR FORT WAYNE, IN March

ST. MARYS RIVER NEAR FORT WAYNE, IN April

ST. MARYS RIVER NEAR FORT WAYNE, IN May

ST. MARYS RIVER NEAR FORT WAYNE, IN June

ST. MARYS RIVER NEAR FORT WAYNE, IN July

ST. MARYS RIVER NEAR FORT WAYNE, IN August

ST. MARYS RIVER NEAR FORT WAYNE, IN September

ST. MARYS RIVER NEAR FORT WAYNE, IN October

ST. MARYS RIVER NEAR FORT WAYNE, IN November

ST. MARYS RIVER NEAR FORT WAYNE, IN December

Sandusky River near Fremont OH January

Sandusky River near Fremont OH February

Sandusky River near Fremont OH March

Sandusky River near Fremont OH April

Sandusky River near Fremont OH

May

Sandusky River near Fremont OH

June

Sandusky River near Fremont OH July

Sandusky River near Fremont OH August

Sandusky River near Fremont OH September

Sandusky River near Fremont OH October

Sandusky River near Fremont OH November

Sandusky River near Fremont OH December

Honey Creek at Melmore OH January

Honey Creek at Melmore OH February

Honey Creek at Melmore OH March

Honey Creek at Melmore OH April

Honey Creek at Melmore OH

May

Honey Creek at Melmore OH

June

Honey Creek at Melmore OH July

Honey Creek at Melmore OH August

Honey Creek at Melmore OH September

Honey Creek at Melmore OH October

Honey Creek at Melmore OH November

Honey Creek at Melmore OH December

Rock Creek at Tiffin OH January

Rock Creek at Tiffin OH February

Rock Creek at Tiffin OH March

Daily non-exceedance probability

Rock Creek at Tiffin OH April

Daily non-exceedance probability

Rock Creek at Tiffin OH May

Rock Creek at Tiffin OH June

Rock Creek at Tiffin OH July

Rock Creek at Tiffin OH August

Rock Creek at Tiffin OH September

Daily non-exceedance probability

Rock Creek at Tiffin OH October

Daily non-exceedance probability

Rock Creek at Tiffin OH November

Rock Creek at Tiffin OH December

Cuyahoga River at Independence OH January

Cuyahoga River at Independence OH February

Cuyahoga River at Independence OH March

Cuyahoga River at Independence OH April

Cuyahoga River at Independence OH

May

Cuyahoga River at Independence OH

June

Cuyahoga River at Independence OH July

Cuyahoga River at Independence OH August

Cuyahoga River at Independence OH September

Cuyahoga River at Independence OH October

Cuyahoga River at Independence OH November

Cuyahoga River at Independence OH December

